

TREASoURcE

D2.6 Scope of learning materials to support CE training

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TREASoURcE

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Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym	Full name
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
CE	Circular Economy
CLIC	CLIC Innovation Ltd
D	Deliverable report
DMP	Data Management Plan
EKOF	Ekokumppanit Oy (EcoFellows)
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
Frstad	Fredrikstad commune
FVH	Forum Virium Helsinki Oy
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KVC	Key value chain
KVC-DEMO	Key value chain demonstration
MTK	The Central Union of Agricultural Producers and Forest Owners
NGO	Non-profit organization
SE	Stakeholder engagement
SE-DEMO	Stakeholder engagement demonstration
TalTech	Tallinna Tehnikaülikool
TARTU	Tartu Linn (Tartu City)
TLN	Tallinna Linn (City of Tallinn)
ØFK	Østfold Fylkeskommune
VTT	VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd
WP	Work package

Executive Summary

In TREASoURcE, children and youth are important stakeholders on the journey towards systemic change towards mainstreaming the circular economy. This deliverable describes in more detail the work the project has done to reach these target groups.

Chapter 2 presents how the circular economy is currently integrated into school curricula in Finland, Norway and Estonia. In all these countries, the circular economy is currently given already some attention in the education of all 7–18-year-olds. In Finland, the circular economy is an integral part of sustainable living in the curricula of basic education, upper secondary schools and vocational education. According to the curricula currently in use, human beings are part of nature and fully dependent on the vitality of ecosystems. Understanding this is central to growing as a human being. Education recognises and acts on the need for sustainable development and guides students towards a sustainable lifestyle. In Norway, all education is based on six principles: dignity, identity and cultural diversity, critical thinking and ethical awareness, the joy of creation, commitment and the need to explore, respect for nature and environmental awareness, and democracy and participation. These all include the theme of sustainable development, and the circular economy is also mentioned as part of sustainable development. Also in Estonia, national curricula emphasise sustainable development as a cross-curricular theme. Although the circular economy is not always explicitly mentioned, its principles are embedded in subjects such as resource conservation, environmental awareness and responsible consumption.

Chapter 3 describes in more detail the activities carried out in the project with the target group, the cooperation within the project and the common learning process. Several project partners have carried out circular economy training and school visits since the early stages of the project. A working group on circular economy training started meetings in August 2024. The working group has shared experiences of training and working with schools and learned from others' examples of possible new ways to deliver circular economy training. The project partners have also carried out nearly 100 training sessions, student projects and school visits to introduce the circular economy to children, young people and their teachers. In addition, various materials have been produced to help schools and other stakeholders to continue circular economy education after the TREASoURcE project will end.

Feedback from teachers on the project's activities in schools has been largely positive. The working group has collected feedback on the measures using a jointly formulated questionnaire. This template can be found in Annex 5.

Chapter 4 presents the working group's dissemination plan, and the follow-up actions already decided and models for cooperation. The working group has planned for the continuation of the training and the dissemination of training concepts and materials will continue actively until the end of the project in spring 2026. Chapter 4 also provides information on where to find the material produced by the project or other material used as a basis for the work of project actors. We hope that the work of the project will be useful for teachers and others working with children and young people interested in circular economy education.

1 Introduction

This document provides an overview of the scope of learning materials to support Circular Economy (CE) training. The aim is to ensure that TREASoURcE works closely with all relevant stakeholders, including children and young people, the education system, and teachers. The work has been conducted internationally, with findings and lessons from different countries being compared, shared, and incorporated into the development of the materials. From this document, you will gain insights into the collaborative efforts made across borders to develop comprehensive CE trainings and training materials. You will learn about the methodologies used, the challenges faced, and the innovative solutions implemented.

In the TREASoURcE project, the work is divided into work packages, each with its own tasks that are relevant to the project's objectives. WP2 - Work Package 2, focuses on stakeholders. Children and young people are involved as external stakeholders in the project because TREASoURcE wants to promote and teach climate-neutral and sustainable CE practices to young people and children as well, as they are a very important stakeholder group. To achieve systemic change towards a circular economy as a way of life, engaging this target group is crucial.

WP2 works in cooperation between the different work packages and ensures that the learning materials supporting CE training are also linked to the TREASoURcE's key value chains (KVC). These KVCs are plastics, batteries for electric vehicles and bio-based side streams. To reduce plastic waste, the aim of the trainings is to get target groups to reflect on their own plastic use. To educate how every one of them can make a personal contribution in reducing plastic waste. The trainings will also raise awareness among children and young people about proper separation to support pro-recycling collection and to understand the importance of recycling. They will also raise awareness of the efficient collection and sorting of waste plastics together with acceptance of recycled products and plastic products made from recycled plastic to increase demand for these products (WP3 Circular plastics value chain). In the context of WP4 (Batteries reuse & recycling value chain), the trainings will raise awareness of the reusability of electric vehicle batteries, raise awareness of electric vehicle batteries as energy storage systems and raise awareness of renewable energy sources such as solar energy. For bio-based side and waste streams (WP5 Circular biobased side and waste streams for biogas and fertilizers), trainings will raise awareness and interest among children and young people in the sorting and collection of biowaste from households for composting and biogas. The trainings will also present how biowaste can be used to produce recycled fertilizers and replace fossil fuels with renewable biogas. (TREASoURcE, 2025)

Youth and children have been engaged in the project by offering educational materials to schools. Youth and children (minors, age of 7-18 and some younger) are mostly engaged via schools and have been audiences in the project and not participated actively in project activities. Their personal data has not been collected. The project partners have produced school materials, which are targeted for children and youth. All information used for the learning materials are age appropriate and they are produced in an easily understandable manner.

2 Background

2.1 Circular Economy in education

2.1.1 Circular Economy in education in Finland

The Finnish education system comprises several stages: early childhood education (before compulsory education), pre-primary education (the year before compulsory education), nine years of general basic education (comprehensive school), upper secondary education (including general and vocational education), and higher education (provided by universities of applied sciences and universities) (Ministry of Education and Culture of Finland, 2025).

TREASoURcE's CE trainings are mainly targeted at children and youth aged 7 – 18. Pupils of this age in Finland are usually in comprehensive school and upper secondary school or vocational education. Therefore, this background study has focused on CE education at these school levels.

2.1.1.1 Circular economy in the basic education (comprehensive school) curriculum

The circular economy is mentioned as one of the value criteria in the 2014 basic education curriculum as part of the necessity of a sustainable lifestyle. According to this current curriculum, humans are part of nature and totally dependent on the vitality of ecosystems. Understanding this is central to growing as a human being. Education recognizes and acts on the need for sustainable development and guides pupils towards a sustainable lifestyle.

The dimensions of sustainability are ecological and economic, social, and cultural. The guiding principle of ecosocial education is to create a way of life and a culture that upholds the integrity of human dignity, the diversity and regenerative capacity of ecosystems, while at the same time building the knowledge base for a circular economy based on the sustainable use of natural resources. Ecosocial education means understanding the seriousness of climate change, and an effort to act sustainably. People develop and use technology and make decisions about technology based on their values. They have the responsibility to steer technology in a direction that will secure the future of people and nature. In basic education the contradictions between consumption and production patterns in relation to a sustainable future are discussed and worked together to find and implement long-term solutions to change our way of life. Pupils are also taught to know social structures and solutions that influence development and how to influence them. Basic education opens the prospect of intergenerational global responsibility. One of the learning objectives is for students to learn to interpret the issues and actions related to the CE and household activities that place a burden on the environment and the economy. (Finnish National Board of Education, 2025).

2.1.1.2 Circular economy in the upper secondary school curriculum

In the current upper secondary school curriculum (2019), the CE is mentioned in the subjects of geography, chemistry, and social studies. The aim is to make students understand the need for a sustainable lifestyle and the importance of a CE that conserves natural resources. Studies strengthen students' ethical and environmental skills by deepening their understanding of different environmental problems and the reasons behind them. It guides students to take responsibility for their own actions and the environment, to use their knowledge of chemistry to build a sustainable future, and to evaluate their own choices in terms of sustainable use of natural resources and the circular economy. It guides students to identify the solutions that chemistry offers to various environmental challenges. Social studies emphasize value-driven and ethical action by the individual for the common good, including social responsibility. It deepens understanding of the principles of the CE and sustainable consumption in the local and global environment. In this way, Social Studies strengthens the student's ethical and environmental competence. (Finnish National Board of Education, 2025).

2.1.1.3 Circular economy in vocational education

In Finland, each qualification in vocational education and training has its own criteria (Finnish National Board of Education, 2025). There is no common curriculum, as in basic and upper secondary education. However, the compulsory general studies in vocational education and training include studies on sustainable development (Finnish National Board of Education, 2025). As an optional studies, vocational education students can study about business opportunities in the circular economy.

2.1.2 Circular Economy in education in Norway

All education in Norway is based in six principles:

- ✓ human dignity,
- ✓ identity and cultural diversity,
- ✓ critical thinking and ethical awareness,
- ✓ joy of creation, engagement, and the urge to explore
- ✓ respect for nature and environmental awareness
- ✓ democracy and participation.

Three overarching themes are integrated in all topics:

- ✓ Public health and life skills
- ✓ Democracy and citizenship
- ✓ Sustainable development

The principles and themes are anchored in the education law, where it is explained that “the students and those who are learning through work, should develop knowledge, skills and attitudes that enable them to master their lives and take part in work and community in society. They should experience the joy of creating, engagement, and the urge to explore. The students and those who are learning through work, should learn critical thinking and to act ethical and environmentally friendly. They should have responsibilities and right to participate” (Directorate of education - government of Norway, 2025). Due to these principles, active and participatory learning methods are a core part of

the Norwegian school system, and the teachers aim to teach topics cross sectionally; integrating mathematics into language classes and integrating environmental issues into mathematics.

Youth Entrepreneurship is a nationwide non-profit organization which collaborates with educational institutions and local businesses on a variety of educational programs, comprising all levels of education from elementary school up to higher education. Youth entrepreneurship has a central role in offering training in innovation and entrepreneurship, which are central skills to experience joy of creation, engagement, and the urge to explore. They are working to better integrate CE principles in their training for teachers and students.

2.1.2.1 Circular Economy in Pre-primary Education

Circular economy is not mentioned in detail in the general core curriculum but is a part of teaching the students environmental awareness and sustainable development. An example of the integration of CE principles can be found in the core curriculum for art and handicraft (age 6-15): “Critical exploration of consumption culture and experience with use and reuse of materials can give the students basis for making ethical choices”. (Directorate of education - government of Norway, 2025)

2.1.2.2 Circular Economy in the Upper Secondary School Curriculum and vocational training

Vocational training is an integrated part of upper secondary school in Norway, and as the students get older, circular economy is described in more detail in relevant topics such as “Nature based business development” (age 17-18), “Electrical energy and communication” (age 16-17), “Engine mechanics” (age 17-18), “Gardening” (age 15-16), etc. CE appears to be better integrated, or at least more clearly outlined, in the more practical secondary educations, than in the curriculum for the students that are choosing the theoretical paths. (Directorate of education - government of Norway, 2025)

2.1.3 Circular Economy in education in Estonia

The Estonian education system comprises pre-primary education (ages 1.5–7), general education (grades 1–12, divided into basic and upper secondary school), vocational education, and higher education provided by universities or professional institutions. CE education in Estonia primarily targets students aged 7–19, corresponding to basic and upper secondary education levels. (Government of the Republic of Estonia, 2024)

2.1.3.1 Circular Economy in Pre-primary Education

The national curriculum for pre-primary education emphasizes environmental awareness and sustainable habits through the thematic area “Me and the Environment.” Children are guided to develop a respectful relationship with nature, notice changes in their surroundings, and learn sustainable practices such as saving resources and reducing waste.

Activities are largely play-based, encouraging children to explore their environment through observation, questioning, and problem-solving. Practical skills, like reusing materials for crafts or learning

about sorting waste, are introduced to build foundational habits for sustainability. (Government of the Republic of Estonia, 2024)

2.1.3.2 Circular Economy in the Basic Education Curriculum

The national curriculum for basic schools emphasizes sustainable development as a cross-curricular theme. While the CE is not explicitly named, its principles are embedded in topics such as resource conservation, environmental awareness, and responsible consumption. These are introduced through natural sciences, civic studies, and technology education.

Students are taught to critically assess the relationship between consumption and environmental impact, fostering sustainable decision-making. Practical activities, such as waste sorting projects and environmental campaigns, complement classroom teaching and encourage eco-friendly habits from an early age. (Government of the Republic of Estonia, 2024)

2.1.3.3 Circular Economy in the Upper Secondary School Curriculum

In upper secondary schools, sustainability themes are integrated into subjects like chemistry, geography, and civic studies. Students analyse global resource challenges and explore solutions rooted in circular economy practices. Chemistry focuses on sustainable materials and technologies, while geography covers resource management and consumption patterns. Civic studies highlight personal and societal roles in advancing sustainability.

The curriculum encourages students to reflect on their consumption habits and understand their impact, promoting critical thinking and responsibility for sustainable development. Optional subjects and extracurricular activities often provide additional opportunities to engage with circular economy concepts. (Government of the Republic of Estonia, 2024)

2.1.3.4 Circular Economy in Vocational Education

In vocational education, sustainability is integrated into field-specific training. While there is no unified curriculum, students explore CE practices tailored to their professions, such as energy-efficient construction or waste management in hospitality.

Optional courses on CE business models and hands-on projects, often in collaboration with local enterprises, provide practical experience. These initiatives highlight the economic and environmental benefits of CE practices, preparing students for real-world application. (Government of the Republic of Estonia, 2024)

3 TREASoURcE Circular Economy trainings

3.1 Co-operation between project partners

3.1.1 Meetings

In the early stages of the project, circular economy trainings were discussed as part of other SE Demos in common WP2 meetings. SE Demos, or Stakeholder Engagement Demos, are a set of different actions that the project takes to promote the circular economy specifically among its many stakeholders. To go deeper into this topic, a working group was set up in August 2024, with a specific focus on CE trainings. The working group was chaired by the EKOF from Finland, responsible for this Deliverable 2.6. Other project partners participating in the working group are Østfold County (Østfold) and City of Fredrikstad (Fredrikstad) from Norway, Forum Virium Helsinki (FVH), CLIC Innovation (CLIC), MTK and Business Tampere (BT) from Finland, City of Tallinn and City of Tartu from Estonia. The working group has been meeting every month in autumn 2024. In January-March 2025, the group has met every two weeks, as the deliverable has been written together.

3.1.2 Target setting

In TREASoURcE's Grant Agreement children and young people, their teachers and the education system are identified as important stakeholders for the project. However, the content or delivery of circular economy trainings is not further defined. Therefore, when the working group started its work, it was important to define its objectives and modus operandi.

As each country and region has different organizations, the working group decided that the CE trainings and materials to be delivered in the project need not be identical. This is because implementation of the results is best achieved when the training and materials are delivered in partnership with existing organizations, which can continue to work with schools after the project has ended. The working group therefore decided to set itself the objective of designing the most appropriate circular economy training(s) for local needs, in cooperation with those organizations who can continue this work permanently.

3.1.3 Learning together

One of the aims of the joint meetings was to learn from other project partners about different models for producing CE training. During the meetings, participants were able to hear the following examples:

- ✓ *Sille Solberg - Young entrepreneurship Østfold*
- ✓ *Kaisa Sibelius/FVH: Enlightened Consumer (The Recycling Master course)*
- ✓ *Jari Saukko and Jaana Koivisto/EKOF: Circular economy trainings based on the socio-constructivist learning approach in the Tampere region.*
- ✓ *Anna Gyüre-Szamosi/Fredrikstad: School visits in Fredrikstad to educate children about the importance of waste sorting, recycling, reuse, and food waste.*
- ✓ *Teele Joost/Tallinn: Lectures on Circular Economy, primarily on the topic of food packaging.*

- ✓ *Marion Kade/Tartu: QualitE project, Tartu Nature House*

The good examples set by the project partners and stakeholders helped other project partners to get tips for improving their own trainings. The joint meetings also provided information on the type of cooperation organizations other project partners have. In addition, joint discussions were held on how to improve the effectiveness of trainings. During the work, participants also gained an understanding of the education systems in different countries and the opportunities they offer for circular economy education.

3.2 Circular Economy trainings

3.2.1 Target groups

The target groups of our trainings were children and youth aged 7-18 years, young adults, and young adults with special needs. Some project partners also involved younger age groups and training was also provided in kindergartens. At the same time, CE information has also been brought to teachers. The materials have been distributed in such a way that teachers can independently continue to use them to teach circular economy after the end of the project activities. During the project, efforts will be made to ensure that all materials are available in public sources and that they will continue to attract operators to keep the information updated.

3.2.2 Trainings in Finland

In Finland, EKOF has carried out a total of 18 CE trainings and three student projects in the Tampere region (Pirkanmaa). FVH has developed The Recycling Master Course, which is described in more detail in chapter 3.2.2.2. CE trainings implemented in Finland are listed in Annex 1.

3.2.2.1 EcoFellows and Tampere region

EcoFellows (EKOF) started the circular economy presentations in schools already in the early stages of the project, in December 2022. Initially, the trainings were more like presentations, with no real pedagogical aspect behind them. Gradually, however, the thinking deepened, and methods began to be devised to help children and young people learn more about circular economy issues and feel that their own involvement was important. The methods used by the EKOF in their trainings were based on a socio-constructivist approach to learning.

Socio-constructivist tendencies emphasize the cultural nature of learning, the importance of community and shared knowledge. Socio-cultural theories of learning emphasize interaction, action and the environment as the starting points and enablers of learning. Thus, learning is a communal process in which knowledge structures are changed through interaction with other people and the environment (Häme University of Applied Sciences, 2025).

In the trainings of EKOF, students were encouraged to engage in a joint reflection activity that best suited their own level of competence, linking the circular economy knowledge to their own previous knowledge and to things they were familiar with in their everyday lives. The trainings targeted upper secondary school students (aged 13 and above), vocational education students, and higher education students. Participants ranged from 13 to 18 years old, including young adults over 18. The circular economy education material produced by the EKOF could easily be applied also to younger age groups, from 7 to 12 years old. However, the schools teaching this age group were not reached for cooperation. The dissemination phase of the results will also aim to reach these target groups.

The material used by EKOF in its trainings has varied slightly depending on the target group of pupils/students. However, experience has shown that the basic structure is as follows:

1. Introducing ourselves. As we are visitors to the school, it's good for children and youth to know who we are. In addition to name, profession and organization, it's also a good idea to tell something deeper about yourself. For example, we've explained why the environment is important to us.
2. Content of the training. We start the trainings by explaining what we will cover during the lesson. This both introduces the students to the subject from the start and gives them a sense of security when they know what to expect. Research has shown that a sense of security improves learning outcomes. See for example: (Salminen, 2023).
3. Participation. It is very important to involve students in the topic through issues related to their own lives. It is therefore important to think more carefully about the target group and what their everyday life is like and how the circular economy can best be introduced there.

In addition to regular training, EKOF has carried out three student projects with educational institutions. The first was the Sprint Innovation Festival at Tampere University of Applied Sciences in spring 2024. FVH also participated in this student project. Sprint Innovation Festival is a series of events that Tampere University of Applied Sciences will continue again in spring 2025. (Sprint Innovation Festival, 2025). TREASoURcE project (EKOF and FVH) was the partner in the 2024 event, commissioning ideas from students on the theme *Mainstreaming Circular Economy*. The second student project was carried out by EKOF together with Tampere Vocational College Tredu. Tredu's offices in Nokia participated in the City of Nokia's Environmental Education Week (Ympäristöviikon ohjelma 2024, 2025). and the project was linked to this. Vocational students were tasked with coming up with ideas to use the circular economy in their professional field. At the end of 2024, EKOF and a group of students from the optional geography course at Tampere Classical Secondary School carried out a research project on *How to get consumers to switch to a circular economy?*

The student projects gave youth a better understanding of the circular economy and helped also project actors to learn new ideas from young people on how to promote the circular economy. Sprint Innovation Festival student teams focused on practical ideas to bring the circular economy closer to people's everyday lives. They ranged from a game to teach circular economy to a handy self-sorting bin for apartment dwellers. The winning idea was selected by EKOF and FVH as a take-away cup and return system for the city's cafés. An honorable mention was given to the repair café idea and this model was also immediately introduced at the TREASoURcE events in autumn 2024.

The students at Tampere Region Vocational College Tredu came from a wide range of industries. In the project, they designed circular economy measures specifically for their own sector. The winning team was a group of students from the horticulture sector, who had an excellent idea of the potential of the circular bioeconomy and the use of side streams in their field.

The students at Tampere Classical Upper Secondary School were asked to investigate how their local community views the circular economy. An interesting finding was that none of the interviewees identified themselves as overconsumers. Figure 1 shows the issues that influence consumer behavior, nicely summarized by Veera Olli, Evert Rännälä and Hilla Waulu, students at Tampere Classical Upper Secondary School. In addition to identifying one's own overconsumption, it is important to appeal to ethical reasons and try to influence people's attitudes. It is also important to recognize that people have different opportunities to change their lifestyles. Finally, how laws and regulations in society guide citizens' behavior is important. (Olli, Rännälä, & Waulu, 2025)

Miten kiertotaloudesta saadaan valtavirtaa?

- Eettisyys (negatiivinen, positiivinen)
- Mahdollisuudet (tulot, asuinpaikka yms.)
- Asenteet (niihin vaikuttaminen, lähipiiri, arvojärjestys)
- Tunnistaa oma ylikuluttaminen (mitä se on, missä raja)
- Yhteiskunnalliset päätökset

Figure 1: How to make the circular economy mainstream? A screenshot of the results of a student project at Tampere Classical Upper Secondary School: Veera Olli, Evert Rännälä and Hilla Waulu

To support its circular economy trainings, EKOF has created materials that provide a concise information package on sustainable consumption, circular economy of plastics, circular economy of batteries and circular bioeconomy (ANNEX 2). In addition, in cooperation with the Fusilli project, Ruokavisa, sustainability education food education material for schools has been implemented (EcoFellows, 2025).

Figure 2: Students from Tampere Classical Upper Secondary School are presenting the results of their research project to EcoFellows in January 2025.

3.2.2.2 Forum Virium Helsinki and The Recycling Master Course

One of the project's targets has been to extend customers' knowledge about recycling. The Recycling Master online course was developed after an evaluation of potential gaps in recycling knowledge. The conclusion was that the needs of different learners were not being met, and they required tailored materials. The goal was to create an accessible, visual, plain text, self-study online training for a target group which is quite often ignored.

We partnered with the Rehabilitative Work Unit and Disability Services of the City of Helsinki to develop the Recycling Master Course concept.

Figure 3: A screenshot from the Recycling Master course in Finnish.

The course includes multiple 45-minute sessions focused on three waste streams from a consumer perspective related to the TREASoURcE project: plastics, bio-waste, and household batteries. In addition to these, there are also sessions covering topics such as a sustainable future and recycling in the workplace. The main driver for creating the course was to bring about a change in individuals' behaviour and habits.

The material includes many videos from various free and publicly available sources. The course is hosted by an avatar that guides students and explains basic terms. The variety of material formats is diverse to help maintain interest.

Figure 4: A screenshot from the Recycling Master course in Finnish.

The online course was designed with the active involvement of adults with developmental disabilities and those on the neurodivergent spectrum, whose functional capacities and support needs vary significantly. This process took place over three co-creation workshops. The course will become part of the city units' official training program at the beginning of 2025, and the units will update and develop the content independently according to their needs. The first feedback from the end-users has been positive and they have indicated that they have already changed and improved their recycling habits. The content can easily be updated if for example some rules have changes, or the course material needs to be modified.

The pilot course was created to Moodle learning platform because it's in use in the city of Helsinki. The Moodle is open-source application, however the installation needs expertise. The concept will also be replicated in Norway and Estonia in collaboration with local entities that are willing to adopt

Figure 5: A screenshot from the Recycling Master course in Finnish.

and utilize it beyond the project's end in 2026. The course will be hosted by FVH until the end of the project in Moodle learning platform and it will be disseminated actively during the time.

3.2.3 Trainings in Norway

In Norway, Østfold and Fredrikstad have carried out a total of 79 CE trainings and two student projects. CE trainings implemented in Norway are listed in Annex 3.

3.2.3.1 Fredrikstad

The experience from local waste collection companies and waste treatment plant is that pre-sorting is the biggest challenge in Fredrikstad. The main challenge with pre-sorting stems from a lack of proper sorting at the source, meaning in households. To address this challenge, Fredrikstad organized a school outreach program aimed at educating children in elementary schools about waste sorting. Children can bring the knowledge they gain at school about waste sorting back to their families and teach their parents how to do it properly. By involving children, we empower them to become ambassadors for sustainable practices within their households. Children often have a natural enthusiasm for learning and sharing new knowledge, which can positively influence family habits. We cooperated with the municipal department that collects waste from households in Fredrikstad and with the local waste treatment plant, FREVAR (*FREVAR KF*). All the training materials were developed together, using already existing relevant content on the topic, and producing new content and tools.

The school outreach program was carried out in 27 classes across 14 schools in 2024 March, September, October and 2025 February and March, engaging approximately 645 children. The target group was 4th-grade students (approximately 9 years old). The program was implemented in a lesson on sustainability, so it was a help for the teachers and not an extra task.

The core activity involved a colourful presentation about waste sorting, recycling and reuse, food and organic waste, biogas, plastic pollution, and sustainability in general. After the presentation the children could test their knowledge in practice through an interactive and enjoyable waste sorting activity and a quiz. This combination of education and interaction proved effective in reinforcing key messages about sustainable waste management and environmental responsibility. After the quiz every child got a diploma that proves that they have completed the training. We asked them to bring it home and show it to their family ensuring that they would also share everything they have learned at the training. We also prepared a colourful poster for each class with the most important rules about waste sorting, which they can put on the wall in the classroom and use it every time they need some guidance.

The schools and teachers expressed high level of satisfaction with the program. They observed that children gained valuable knowledge about waste sorting and found the program interactive enough to maintain their interest and engagement. Several teachers shared feedback that they themselves learned new information about waste sorting and sustainability. This highlights the dual benefit of the

program, enhancing not only the students' understanding but also equipping educators with useful knowledge. Teachers acknowledged that they lack sufficient knowledge and capacity to educate children about waste sorting and sustainability effectively. They appreciated the municipality's initiative to take on this responsibility and emphasized the importance of such efforts.

It is worth mentioning that the waste sorting exercise part of this training was also carried out at the biggest yearly family festival in Fredrikstad, the World Children's Day (Barnas Verdensdag) and at the Lisleby Culture Festival at Lisleby community centre in the spring of 2024. These SE-demos were not carried out at schools, but they play an equally important role in educating students, as the primary target group of these festivals are children and youth. Furthermore, festivals attract a lot of people, so they are very effective ways to deliver the most important messages about sustainability to a large audience.

Figure 6: Waste sorting presentation and activity for children.

Figure 7: Picture of Quiz, about the diploma Frstad gives to every child, about the poster Frstad leaves for the class.

3.2.3.2 Østfold

In Østfold, the focus has been on cooperating with actors such as NGOs that already have activities in the schools and are able to assist them in including circular economy in ordinary school activities. We have focused on two actors: Inspiria Science Center, and Youth Entrepreneurship.

The County Council has cooperated with Inspiria Science Center for several years, offering schools all over the county activity days focusing on bicycles. Between April and October 2024, 62 activity days were carried out, and 2650 students got their bicycles serviced to ensure they are safe for use and will last longer. They also received training in how to do simple repairs on their own bikes, and increased general knowledge on climate, environment, and circular economy. Through the TREASoURcE project, Inspiria has developed a teaching programme for circular economy, utilizing both the waste sorting trailer that was developed in connection to the CE events task, and these activity days. The teaching programme is being further developed in cooperation with Østfold Avfallssortering (ØAS) and will be offered to schools in the years to come.

Youth Entrepreneurship Østfold has an Interreg Norway-Sweden project focusing on how to better integrate circular economy in business development classes. By cooperation with the NGO, Østfold county council has taken advantage of synergies and increased the output of both projects. May 14th, 2024, Ostfold took part in the Interreg project kick off activity at Strømstad upper secondary school in Sweden. 71 Norwegian and 73 Swedish students took part in the day, which included presentations about TREASoURcE, the new waste sortment system in Østfold, and the new textile recycling industry being developed in Sweden. The students also participated in a cross-border workshop, where mixed groups of Swedish and Norwegian students cooperated to develop new circular business ideas. September 9th, 2024, TREASoURcE and circular economy principles were presented at the kick off for all student businesses in Østfold, with 612 students and 27 teachers participating. The students will be developing their businesses throughout the school year of 2024/2025, with the goal of winning the European championship of youth businesses in Athens, Greece, in July 2025. On the way to the European championship, there are also local, regional, and national competitions, and circular economy is one the criteria the businesses will be measured by.

CE-training in secondary schools: underutilized food resources

September 17th-18th 2024, 15 students and 3 teachers at the Kirkeparken upper secondary school for chefs spent two days on a circular economy innovation camp. TREASoURcE provided ingredients that are normally wasted or used for animal feed, such as large carrots and beets, local fruit, low protein flour, yellow peas and fava beans, blood, and spent grain from beer production. The students developed and tested a variety of recipes and competed about making the best food.

Figure 8: Charcutier board including blood chips, flat bread from feed grade vegetables, chutney from waste grade local fruit.

Figure 9: Bread from feed grain and fruit leather from local waste grade fruit.

Figure 10: Jury contemplating the different entries.

Figure 11: Winners of the competition.

Figure 12: Video from the innovation camp can be found in YouTube. <https://youtu.be/K89msZITWkl>. (Klima Østfold, 2025)

December 21st, 2024 was the kick-off for the student business project at Tindlund lower secondary school with all 101 students and 3 teachers at grade 9, primarily within the subject of food and health. The students have received presentations on circular economy principles and have been challenged to make business ideas based on underutilized food resources, like feed grain and oddly shaped vegetables, and implement these ideas. In the process the students are given resources and facts on underutilized food resources in their region and nationwide. A competition on presenting dishes, chef's championship, based on the underutilized food resources was executed 13-15.02.2025 with judges from Young Entrepreneurship and County of Østfold. The project will run further into the spring of 2025.

CE-training of teacher students

October 17th, 2024, and December 4th, 79 teacher students at the University college of Østfold, got an introduction to TREASoURcE and circular economy principles. Based on this, they developed cross-disciplinary teaching plans for 556 students ranging from 7- to 17-year-old.

For the youngest students, the teaching plans were implemented in 25 classes October 31st and November 1st. The focus was on the reduction of squandering and mass consumption, particularly in connection to toys. Some groups focused on alternatives to wasteful spending of resources for Halloween and for Christmas. The goal was to enlighten and empower the children through the challenge of developing inventions.

Figure 13: Stop squandering invention: vacuums up toys that are no longer in use, repairs them and makes them more interesting.

The second group of college students focused on pupils in the age group 15-19 in 6 different schools, including both theoretical classes and vocational training. They developed a wide range of teaching programs, some examples include:

- ✓ Arts and handicrafts: learning about different types of textiles, their properties and environmental impact, focusing on wool and wool production.
- ✓ Music: Learning to make their own musical instruments from waste, visiting recycling centers to find the materials needed.
- ✓ Health and growing up: The students got the task of interviewing elderly, both with Norwegian and immigrant backgrounds, to learn more about the different attitudes and practices of waste and consumption then and now, focusing on food and textiles.

3.2.4 Trainings in Estonia

In Estonia Tallinn has carried out a total of 65 CE trainings in kindergartens and schools. CE trainings implemented in Estonia are listed in Annex 4.

3.2.4.1 Tallinn's educational program Wastewolf

During the 2024–2026 school years, Tallinn implements the educational program “Prevention and Reduction of Waste Generation, Reuse and Recycling, and Developing the Habit of Waste Sorting.” The program involves preparing, organizing, and conducting lessons in Tallinn’s kindergartens,

schools, and some public events held in the city. The target audience includes kindergarten children aged 5–7 and students from grades 1–4.

The program focuses on topics such as waste prevention and reduction, reuse, and recycling, and fostering the habit of sorting waste.

The city of Tallinn has conducted awareness campaigns on environmentally sustainable consumption and waste sorting for several years, focusing primarily on raising environmental awareness among children. The environmental education program is a continuation of the sustainable consumption campaign "Wastewolf 2015–2017" in Tallinn, introducing children to sustainable lifestyles, waste reduction, recycling, waste sorting, the basics of the circular economy, including the issue of marine litter, and ways to prevent and reduce it.

During the 2024–2026 school years, a total of 1 290 lessons will be conducted in Tallinn's educational institutions, involving an estimated 29 000 children. In Tallinn's educational institutions, each lesson conducted as part of the educational program will last 45 minutes. A single lesson is designed for at least one group or class, comprising an estimated 24 children.

Each lesson will be conducted by at least two facilitators, one of whom must wear a "Wastewolf" mascot costume. The lessons will engage participants actively in the learning process and include playing environmental-themed games.

Participants will be introduced to key environmental concepts through various teaching materials and examples:

- ✓ Sustainable Consumption: How to consume daily in ways that minimize waste and reduce ecological footprints.
- ✓ Reuse and Recycling: Practical ways to reuse items, recycle waste, and return materials to circulation.
- ✓ Waste Sorting: How to properly sort waste, where to take sorted waste, and what happens to it after collection.

The session begins with a discussion about the types and amounts of waste generated in households. Children will be introduced to waste-related terms, many of which will be new to them.

1. Waste Sorting Game:

- a. Participants will sort a pile of waste into six different bins:
 - i. Brown: Bio-waste
 - ii. Yellow: Plastic and metal packaging, beverage cartons
 - iii. Green: Glass packaging
 - iv. Blue: Paper and cardboard
 - v. Gray: Mixed waste
 - vi. Red: Hazardous waste
- b. Facilitators will review the sorted waste, correct any mistakes, and explain the reasoning behind proper sorting.

- c. This hands-on activity is the most critical part of the session, as it provides practical experience that children can apply at home.

To conclude, children will be shown examples of materials made from recycled waste, emphasizing the importance of waste sorting for creating new products.

Figure 14: Wastewolf and his good friend are talking to kindergarten children about waste sorting.

The program aligns with the national curricula for pre-primary and basic education, which aim to support children's individuality, creativity, and learning through play. Environmental education promotes a value-based approach to nature and sustainable development. Children will learn to:

- ✓ Act responsibly toward nature,
- ✓ Recognize and understand environmental problems,
- ✓ Comprehend the interconnections between humans and the environment,
- ✓ Take actions that conserve natural resources.

Facilitators will guide children to observe, ask questions (identify problems), hypothesize and test their assumptions, and draw conclusions based on their observations and experiences.

The lessons will use the following materials to ensure an engaging and educational experience:

- ✓ Waste sorting bins and pictograms for bio-waste (brown), plastic and metal packaging/beverage cartons (yellow), glass packaging (green), paper/cardboard (blue), mixed waste (gray), and hazardous waste (red).
- ✓ Examples of appropriate waste for sorting.
- ✓ Samples of recycled materials.
- ✓ Roll-up banners on waste topics, provided by the contracting authority.
- ✓ Items illustrating reuse.
- ✓ Environmental-themed board games, treasure hunt-style games, and similar activities for public events.

- ✓ Facilitators' attire, including a teaching costume and a "Wastewolf" mascot costume.

Figure 15: After the training, each child receives a workbook from Wastewolf to help reinforce what they have learned.

This program ensures that children not only gain theoretical knowledge but also practical skills, fostering environmentally conscious behavior and promoting sustainable development in their communities.

To ensure that waste sorting does not remain just a briefly learned theory but becomes a part of everyday practice, Tallinn has provided waste sorting container sets to every kindergarten and school in the city. These sets allow children to separately dispose of biowaste, paper, clean packaging, and mixed waste. Additionally, many schools have placed extra containers in hallways for collecting deposit packaging, enabling them to collect refundable bottles and cans.

3.2.4.2 Seminar on packaging materials and their environmental impact

In middle schools, the topic of waste is covered only minimally, as the curriculum focuses on traditional subjects like biology, geography, and chemistry. While these subjects are indirectly connected to waste and its environmental impact, they rarely address these connections in depth. This gap left us uncertain about how much middle school students think about waste generation or sorting, and how familiar they are with related concepts.

The seminar was structured to balance education with engagement. It included slides and a presentation that provided new information, but each topic was preceded by a discussion. These discussions aimed to encourage critical thinking and gauge students' existing knowledge about packaging and waste. Due to time restriction — the seminar lasted only one lesson period (45 minutes) — we focused on the most essential topics. These included key packaging materials such as glass, metal, cardboard, and plastics, including biodegradable plastics. We explored their properties, durability in nature, and environmental impact. With each material, we also talked about its recyclability and how to collect it separately.

The seminar took place in a large auditorium with about 70 students from three classes attending at a time. While this setup allowed us to reach a broad audience quickly, it limited the opportunity for hands-

on activities or group work. Maintaining engagement with such a large group required interactive discussions and direct participation.

As expected, students' prior knowledge on these topics was limited, with many incorrect answers during discussions. However, it was encouraging to see their active participation and curiosity throughout the seminar. By the end, students gained a better understanding of different packaging materials, their environmental effects, and the importance of proper waste sorting.

The seminar provided valuable insights for us as facilitators. While large-group settings are efficient for reaching many students in a short time, they limit the depth of engagement. In the future, conducting sessions for individual classes may allow for more interactive and hands-on approaches, such as group activities or games. Ultimately, the format may depend on the school's preferences and resources.

Figure 16: Tallinn City representative Teele Joost speaking to Laagna School's students about the topic of reusable packaging.

Despite the challenges, the seminar achieved its goal of raising awareness and sparking interest among students about waste and sustainability. This experience highlighted the importance of tailoring environmental education to young learners and confirmed the need for further initiatives in this area.

3.2.5 Feedback

Feedback on the trainings was collected through a jointly developed questionnaire, which was translated into the language of each target country (ANNEX 5).

3.2.5.1 Feedback in Finland

EKOF sent a link to the feedback survey to teachers after the CE training sessions. The responses were mostly positive, but there were some suggestions for improvement. One of the suggestions for improvement was to pay attention to ensuring that the words and terms used are understandable to the age group of pupils. In addition, the training for students with special needs was praised for its very illustrative and practical material, but it was also asked to consider that the ability to concentration of the target group is very limited.

The EliCo Recycling Master course has been in official use only for few weeks, but the course has received positive feedback. However, due to users' different abilities the slow progress of the course has received some comments.

3.2.5.2 Feedback in Norway

Fredrikstad municipality sent a link to the feedback survey to teachers after the school visits. All the teachers who participated in the survey stated that the students learned something new about circular economy and waste sorting and found the training very useful. They also said they would recommend the program to other teachers. Additionally, 80% of the teachers reported that they themselves gained new knowledge from the training. When asked whether students' understanding, attitudes, or behavior regarding sustainability and waste sorting had changed after the visit, the responses indicated that students had become better at recycling and more conscious of sorting waste in the classroom. All teachers agreed that the practical exercises, where students could actively participate, were the most effective teaching method. They observed that students tend to remember best when learning through hands-on activities. No teachers reported any challenges related to the school visit, and they did not feel that anything was missing from the teaching program. However, 20% believed that incorporating even more practical exercises could further improve the training program.

In Østfold the feedback was given through surveys and in evaluation meetings for the different events involving Youth Entrepreneurship. For the teaching students the particular focus on circular economy was a very effective way of producing more relevant teaching programs that could satisfy cross-disciplinary themes. Teachers reported that the different process methods provided by Youth Entrepreneurship on innovation and creative work were very effective in terms of being able to sharpen and refine ideas and the particular focus on circular economy was very helpful as a way of framing and delineating the creative efforts.

The pupils working with business ideas and dishes related to underutilized food resources reported that they have become more aware of how they can use alternative raw materials, this was especially true of pupils at upper secondary chef's vocational training.

3.2.5.3 Feedback in Estonia

Tallinn sent a link to the feedback survey to teachers after the CE training sessions. The feedback was largely positive, though some areas for improvement were highlighted. One of the suggestions for improvement was the need for a separate training session specifically for teachers. Although teachers do participate in the Wastewolf lesson, their role in the classroom primarily focuses on maintaining order and supervision. It was suggested that a dedicated training session should be provided to enhance teachers' own knowledge and understanding of the topic. Additionally, attention should be given to ensuring that the language and terms used are appropriate for the pupils' age group. The training for students with special needs received praise for its highly illustrative and practical material, but it was also noted that the concentration ability of this target group is quite limited.

4 Next steps

4.1 Co-operation with schools and other stakeholders

During the project, EKOF has offered circular economy trainings to all interested schools in Pirkanmaa region. Now that the concept and materials are ready, EKOF will focus on disseminating the model in schools in the city of Tampere. One reason for this is that with a smaller target group, it is easier to find people responsible for continuing the training after the project has ended. On the other hand, the schools of the city of Tampere have a working group on eco-social education, through which the dissemination of the trainings is easy.

FVH has presented the EliCo Recycling Master course and the concept for some potential stakeholders in Finland and the material is easy to adopt in the cases when the organization has Moodle already in use. FVH can run Moodle until the end of the project in 2026.

Fredrikstad will continue with the school visits. Many schools suggested that the program should not only continue but also expand in 2025 to reach more children and deepen its impact. In response to this feedback, we have already begun planning for the continuation and expansion of the school visit program. Indeed, several schools have already applied for the program in 2025. We are also working with a book manuscript, which will be given to schools after our visits. It is going to be an illustrated storybook from which children can playfully learn about waste collection. The book itself is expected to be ready in the fall of 2025. Our goal is to include older students in the program, both middle school and high school students, with content that is appropriate for their age group. Our cooperation partner in that will be Youth Entrepreneurship, a non-profit, nationwide organization that already has activities in schools and experience with circular economy education. Planning of activities is already underway. We are going to conduct innovation camps for 8th graders at 3-4 middle schools and 2 high schools in Fredrikstad. The camps will be conducted over 1-2 days at the end of this school year, so before summer 2025. In Østfold dissemination and exchange of experience on key learning points with the circular economy training programs will be done through the collaboration with Youth Entrepreneurship to deepen the impact of the training. This will be done later in the spring 2025 through webinars and seminars for teachers and parts of teacher's seminars on circular business models. Østfold will continue the collaboration with Youth Entrepreneurship on circular economy training and innovation teaching and will plan for an innovation camp on underutilized food resources at lower secondary level late spring 2025. Concepts for secondary schools on pupil's and student businesses for design/re-design of textiles will be considered for autumn 2025, but conclusive plans and selection of programs will be discussed throughout spring 2025.

Tallinn will continue with the Wastewolf program, which has proven to be a well-established and effective initiative. Our team is highly motivated, and they have a clear understanding of how to conduct the training sessions. The program successfully engages the youngest age group, planting the seed for responsible waste management habits that can last a lifetime. However, one training session in early childhood is not enough. The seminar held in the fall provided us with a clear insight that

packaging-related topics also need to be addressed with middle school students. Therefore, we plan to conduct additional packaging-related seminars in schools throughout 2025. In addition, we are exploring new approaches, such as collaborating with the leaders of entrepreneurship education program for school students, which could offer targeted initiatives for both middle and high school students.

4.2 Dissemination plan

The working group considered the dissemination of the CE trainings as soon as it started its work. It was decided that the best way to establish circular economy training as part of normal school activities would be to cooperate with organizations whose activities would continue after the end of the project. This is why the team chose this approach, rather than building a single training model for the whole project. Under the guidance of WP8 leader Kaisa Simola (CLIC), the working group also prepared a separate dissemination plan in a workshop in January 2025.

Figure 17: Screenshot from the Miro tool: TREASoURcE CE trainings - Dissemination Planning 17.1.2025. This tool is adapted from the work licensed under CC BY-SA 4.0.CC by Open Innovation Playbook by CLIC Innovation.

As the training sessions have been slightly different for each project partner and so also the cooperation with different organizations, the dissemination and implementation plans will naturally also differ slightly between the different project partners. However, there were some common features in the results of the Dissemination Planning workshop and the project partners again got good ideas and tips from each other.

One common feature was that project actors felt that the dissemination task was clearly best carried out through cooperation, participation and communication. In contrast, actual consultation was perceived as the least suitable option. However, decision-makers and administrators, for example, as well as other organizations working with schools, appear to be a potential target group for consultation.

Naturally, teachers were also seen by all as an important target group with whom to disseminate circular economy education.

Table 1 Dissemination Plan.

Target group		Engagement method/channel
Collaborate	Teachers at different educational levels (especially teachers who are already familiar with the subject), Municipal officials, NGOs, Nature and environmental education centres, Other projects and youth programs, Businesses.	Meetings with teachers, seminars, webinars, workshops, conferences, fairs, Contacting by email, Podcasts, social media channels, School visits, Specific channels, such as the Youth Entrepreneurship Teachers Portal (Ostfold), the Ecosocial Education Teachers Group (EKOF), Materials available online.
Involve	Teachers at different educational levels (especially teachers who are already familiar with the subject), NGOs, Nature and environmental education centres, Creators of science teaching materials, Other local stakeholders for example heads of education in municipalities.	Meetings, seminars, webinars, Materials available online.
Consult	Companies that carry out social or community projects and promote environmental education, Municipal education department, Other organizations collaborating with schools.	
Inform	Teachers at different educational levels (especially teachers who are	Meetings with teachers, seminars, webinars, workshops,

	already familiar with the subject), Schools and other service providers for students with special needs, Moodle users (EliCo), Recycling and waste management companies, Decision-makers in municipalities, Teachers' unions, General public.	Podcasts, blogs, YouTube and other social media channels, Materials available online (TREASoURcE, project partners' websites), In Fredrikstad, a storybook is being produced and will be distributed to schools after the visits. It will be an illustrated storybook that children can use to learn about waste collection in a playful way. The manuscript can be translated into other languages.
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4.3 Circular economy teaching materials for primary school, upper secondary school and vocational school

There is already a wide range of circular economy educational material available for children, young people and teachers at national level in all project countries.

In Finland, the work utilized materials from Sitra, among others. Sitra and over 50 educational institutions, training organizations, and companies have designed and piloted circular economy learning materials and teaching modules for primary schools, high schools, vocational schools, and universities. We built the work by utilizing the existing materials. (Sitra, 2025)

EliCo Recycling Master course utilized plenty of various public and free of use material published by the following organizations: Helsinki Region Environmental Services HSY (e.g. Jäteopas (HSY - Helsingin seudun ympäristöpalvelut, 2025), National Broadcasting Company YLE, an association of public waste management and municipal waste facilities KIVO (Suomen Kiertovoima ry (KIVO), 2025), Regional Recycling company Kierrätyskeskus (Kierrätyskeskus, 2025), the manager the return systems of beverage packages PalPa (Suomen palautuspakkaus oy (Palpa), 2025) and a packaging recycling developer Sumi Oy (Sumi Oy, 2025).

In Norway, the activities focused on cooperation with NGOs on how to utilize existing tools and materials through practical training, with the goal of providing the students with opportunities to be creative, committed, and inquisitive, and experience the joy of creating. The training programmes developed in Østfold, will be available for schools all over Norway and our neighbour region in Sweden through Youth entrepreneurship's national and international network (Ungt Entreprenørskap, 2025).

In Fredrikstad the activities focused on cooperation with local schools. We cooperated also with the municipal department that collects waste from households in Fredrikstad and with the local waste treatment plant, FREVAR (*FREVAR KF*). All the training materials for the school visits were developed together, using already existing relevant content on the topic and also producing new content. We are working with a storybook, which will be given to schools after our visits. It is going to be an illustrated storybook from which children can playfully learn about waste collection. The book tells the story of Trygve the fox, who lives deep in the forest. His best friend is Anna the hedgehog, who gets injured by trash that someone has left behind in the forest. Trygve becomes distressed and angry about all the waste threatening their home and decides to do something about it. The book itself is expected to be ready in the fall of 2025. The method and the materials developed for the school visit series will also be made available to all schools.

Figure 18: Storybook of Trygve the Fox.

Various organizations in Estonia provide educational materials on the circular economy, making resources available in Estonian for different age groups. Eesti Pakendiringlus has developed a comprehensive activity book aimed at children aged 6–12, featuring games, craft instructions, and exercises to teach waste sorting and recycling in an engaging way (Eesti Pakendiringlus OÜ, 2023). Tootjavastutusorganisatsioon (TVO) offers detailed sorting instructions and provides free educational classes for schools to promote awareness of packaging, waste prevention, and proper waste management (Tootjavastutusorganisatsioon OÜ, 2025). The *VIDEOÕPS* YouTube channel covers a broad range of environmental topics, including circular economy concepts, making them accessible to a wider audience (Videoõps, 2025). For older learners, Zero Waste Estonia provides training materials, guides, and tools to support waste-free management and circular economy practices, while the Ministry of Climate offers resources on transitioning from waste management to a circular economy, focusing on

sustainability policies and solutions (Zero Waste Estonia SA, 2025) (Ministry of Climate, 2025). Additionally, the *Circular Classroom* initiative has made its interactive educational toolkit available in Estonian, equipping upper secondary educators and students with structured materials, including videos, workbooks, and activities, to integrate circular thinking into learning (Co-Founders, 2025). This list is not exhaustive, and there may be additional materials available that have not yet been mapped.

In Tartu, the Tartu Nature House (*Tartu loodusmaja*) offers diverse environmental education programs for children of all ages, fostering a connection with nature and promoting sustainable habits. The Tartu Nature School, an eco-friendly hobby school, engages over 500 children and young people annually in hands-on activities that teach environmental responsibility. Through interactive workshops, nature excursions, and creative projects, children learn about biodiversity, waste reduction, and circular economy principles in a playful and engaging way. Additionally, the Nature House coordinates international initiatives like the Eco-Schools Global program and the UNESCO Associated Schools Baltic Sea Project, integrating sustainability education into school curricula. By providing a dynamic learning environment, Tartu Nature House plays a key role in shaping environmentally conscious future generations. (Tartu Keskkonnahariduse Keskus, 2025)

CE training materials developed by TREASoURcE will be published on the project website (TREASoURcE project, 2025).

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ANNEX 1 – Trainings in Finland

Date	Theme of the training	Level of school/grade	Age of the pupils/students	More detailed description
14.12.2022	Circular Economy and TREA-SoURcE project	Upper secondary school	16-18	EKOF / Helsinki Upper Secondary School of Languages visited Tampere
6.3.2023	Circular Economy and TREA-SoURcE project	Ahlman Vocational College	16-	EKOF / Ahlman's undergraduate students in nature, environment and greenery
28.3.2023	A theme day focusing specifically on the circular economy of plastics, where two 7th grade secondary school classes visited the Tampere Vocational College Tredu to learn about the processing of recycled plastic.	Tampere Vocational College Tredu, Viljakkala Secondary School 7th grade, Vesilahti Secondary School 7th grade	16- and 13-14	EKOF / Tampere University presentation on marine plastics, Tredu plastics recycling process presentation and student experiments, circular economy quiz
24.4.2023	Presentation: circular economy and environmental	Ikaalinen Vocational College of Crafts and Design	16-	EKOF / Presentation for the students and their teachers

	responsibility in educational institutions			
29.5.2023	CE training	Secondary School 7th grade in Pälkäne	13 – 14	EKOF / CE training/presentation
28.11.2023	CE training/presentation	Hakkari Secondary School in Lempäälä, 7 th , 8 th and 9 th grades	13-15	EKOF / CE training/presentation
15.2. – 15.3.2024	Sprint Innovation Festival in Tampere University of Applied Sciences	Higher education students	18-	<p>EKOF & FVH / At the Sprint Innovation Festival, interdisciplinary teams of students tackle challenges, with input from our working life partners offering various perspectives. The partners accompany the students throughout the process, providing support and fuelling the teams to generate new and innovative ideas.</p> <p>Students can apply the skills they have learned in their studies and develop meta-skills such as teamwork and creativity.</p> <p>As the grand finale of the Sprint event, the representatives from working life partners assess the solutions and select the best ones, which are also rewarded.</p>
6.5.2024	CE training	Upper secondary school students from Tampere Classical Upper Secondary School	16-	Students from Tampere Classical Upper Secondary School visited EKOF office.

20.8.- 1.10.2024	EliCo concept workshops	Adults	18 -	Three EliCo concept development workshops with the customers and personnel of Rehabilitative Work Activities and Disability Service Unit of the City of Helsinki
9.9. – 20.9.2024	Circular economy competition for students in upper secondary education (vocational education)	Vocational education students studying at Tredu's locations in the city of Nokia	16-	EKOF / The circular economy competition was part of the City of Nokia's Environmental Education Week programme
7.10. – 1.11.2024	CE trainings	Secondary School 9 th grade in Tampere, Hatanpää school	15-16	EKOF / Lessons with an environmental ethics focus
8.10.2024	CE training	Kiipula Vocational School for Special Needs, Preparatory Education	16-	EKOF / Students with special needs
25.11.2024	CE training	Hakkari Secondary School in Lempäälä, 7th, 8th and 9th grades	13-15	EKOF / CE training
13.12.2024 – 27.1.2025	Student project, attitudes towards the circular economy	Upper secondary school students from Tampere Classical Upper Secondary School	16-	EKOF / Research course linked to geography studies

ANNEX 2 – Learning materials to support CE training/EcoFellows

Figure 19: EKOF uses the following presentation material to support its circular economy training.

ANNEX 3 – Trainings in Norway

Date	Theme of the training	Level of school/grade	Age of the pupils	More detailed description
07.03.2024	Training about waste sorting, recycling, food waste and sustainability	elementary school / 4 th grade	9-10	Frstad / school visit at Childrens' International School The core activity involved presentation and an interactive and enjoyable waste sorting exercise and quiz. Topics: waste sorting, recycling, food waste, organic waste, plastic pollution, sustainability
08.03.2024	Training about waste sorting, recycling, food waste and sustainability	elementary school / 4 th grade	9-10	Frstad / school visit at Torsnes School The core activity involved presentation and an interactive and enjoyable waste sorting exercise and quiz. Topics: waste sorting, recycling, food waste, organic waste, plastic pollution, sustainability
01.04-25.10.2024	Circular economy & repair and maintenance of bicycles	Pupils at elementary & lower secondary school level	10-15	62 activity days, 2650 pupils reached Learning about climate gas emissions, maintenance of bikes and how to do simple repairs on your own bike
14.05.2024	Integration of circular economy in business development training.	Pupils at upper secondary schools	16-18	Kick-off for 73 students from schools in southern Ostfold. Presentation of TREASoURcE, waste sorting systems in Ostfold, training about emerging textile recycling industry
9.9.2024	Developing CE student businesses, underutilized food, plastic and textile waste	Pupils at upper secondary schools, entrepreneurial teaching	15-18	Presentation on circular economy themes and entrepreneurial methods for 612 students and 26 teachers, kick-off for developing student businesses from schools all throughout the county of Østfold.
17.-18.09 2024	Underutilized food resources	Pupils at upper secondary school,	18	15 students, 3 teachers, Kirkeparken upper secondary school. Innovation camp & competition, presentation on

	and making new dishes from these	chef's and restaurant subject		underutilized food resources and making of dishes from resources like feed grain, waste grade fruit, spent brewery grain, large carrots etc.
17.09.2024	Training about waste sorting, re-cycling, food waste and sustainability	elementary school / 4 th grade	9-10	Frstad / school visit at Hurrød School The core activity involved presentation and an interactive and enjoyable waste sorting exercise and quiz. Topics: waste sorting, recycling, food waste, organic waste, plastic pollution, sustainability
18.09.2024	Training about waste sorting, re-cycling, food waste and sustainability	elementary school / 4 th grade	9-10	Frstad / school visit at Slevik School The core activity involved presentation and an interactive and enjoyable waste sorting exercise and quiz. Topics: waste sorting, recycling, food waste, organic waste, plastic pollution, sustainability
19.09.2023	Training about waste sorting, re-cycling, food waste and sustainability	elementary school / 4 th grade	9-10	Frstad / school visit at Nøkleby School The activity involved presentation and an interactive and enjoyable waste sorting exercise and quiz. Topics: waste sorting, recycling, food waste, organic waste, plastic pollution, sustainability
20.09.2024	Training about waste sorting, re-cycling, food waste and sustainability	elementary school / 4 th grade	9-10	Frstad/school visit at Ambjørnrød School The core activity involved presentation and an interactive and enjoyable waste sorting exercise and quiz. Topics: waste sorting, recycling, food waste, organic waste, plastic pollution, sustainability
23.09.2024	Training about waste sorting, re-cycling, food waste and sustainability	elementary school / 4 th grade	9-10	Frstad / school visit at Begby School The core activity involved presentation and an interactive and enjoyable waste sorting exercise and quiz. Topics: waste sorting, recycling, food waste, organic waste, plastic pollution, sustainability
24.09.2024	Training about waste sorting, re-cycling, food waste and sustainability	elementary school / 4 th grade	9-10	Frstad / school visit at Manstad School The activity involved presentation and an interactive and enjoyable waste sorting exercise and quiz. Topics: waste sorting, recycling, food waste, organic waste, plastic pollution, sustainability

15.10.2024	Training about waste sorting, recycling, food waste and sustainability	elementary school / 4 th grade	9-10	Frstad / school visit at Lunde School The activity involved presentation and an interactive and enjoyable waste sorting exercise and quiz. Topics: waste sorting, recycling, food waste, organic waste, plastic pollution, sustainability
16.10.2024	Training about waste sorting, recycling, food waste sustainability	elementary school / 4 th grade	9-10	Frstad / school visit at Kjølberg School The activity involved presentation and an interactive and enjoyable waste sorting exercise and quiz. Topics: waste sorting, recycling, food waste, organic waste, plastic pollution, sustainability
17.10.2024 31.10 & 1.11 1.12.2024	Develop cross-disciplinary CE-training programs/ mini-projects	Students of teaching for elementary schools, both vocational and theoretical training, upper secondary level	6-13, 16-18	Innovation camp for students of teaching at University College of Østfold, presentations on circular economy principles. Develop cross-disciplinary CE-training programs. Results: 79 students, implementing programs for 556 pupils on wide range of subjects including -program on inventive reduction of wasteful consumption of toys (7–13-year-olds) - program for arts and crafts-students - program for students of music - program for students of health and education
January-March 2025	General CE-training and developing business ideas on underutilized food resources	Pupils at lower secondary school, subject of food and health	15	101 Pupils from Tindlund lower secondary school, training on circular economy themes, in particular underutilized food resources. Learning on underutilized food resources in Ostfold, how to create pupils' businesses and business ideas based on underutilized food resources. Competition on dishes 13-15.02
26.02.2025	Training about waste sorting, recycling, food waste sustainability	elementary school / 4 th grade	9-10	Frstad / school visit at Trara School The activity involved presentation and an interactive and enjoyable waste sorting exercise and quiz. Topics: waste sorting, recycling, food waste, organic waste, plastic pollution, sustainability

27.02.2025	Training about waste sorting, recycling, food waste sustainability	elementary school / 4 th grade	9-10	Frstad / school visit at CIS School The activity involved presentation and an interactive and enjoyable waste sorting exercise and quiz. Topics: waste sorting, recycling, food waste, organic waste, plastic pollution, sustainability
03.03.2025	Training about waste sorting, recycling, food waste sustainability	elementary school / 4 th grade	9-10	Frstad / school visit at Rødmyra School The activity involved presentation and an interactive and enjoyable waste sorting exercise and quiz. Topics: waste sorting, recycling, food waste, organic waste, plastic pollution, sustainability
05.03.2025	Training about waste sorting, recycling, food waste sustainability	elementary school / 4 th grade	9-10	Frstad / school visit at Hauge School The activity involved presentation and an interactive and enjoyable waste sorting exercise and quiz. Topics: waste sorting, recycling, food waste, organic waste, plastic pollution, sustainability

ANNEX 4 – Trainings in Estonia

Date	Theme of the training	Level of school/grade	Age of the pupils	More detailed description
05.09.2024	Waste-wolf lesson about waste sorting.	Kindergarden	5-7 years	Mina Oskan Seda kindergarden, Lasteaed Män-
09.09.2024				nimudila kindergarde, Padriku kindergarden, Ra-
10.09.2024				barüblük Lasteaed, Arbu kindergarden, Rabarüb-
11.09.2024				lik kindergarden, Kraavikröll kindergarden, Liikuri
12.09.2024				kindergarden, Kirsike kindergarden, Merivälja
13.09.2024				kindergarden, Kirsike kindergarden, Kurisiku kin-
16.09.2024				dergarden, Pallasti kindergarden, Mahtra kinder-
17.09.2024				garden, Pae kindergarden, Rännaku kindergar-
18.09.2024				den, Mustakivi kindergarden, Lauliku kindergar-
20.09.2024				den, Mustakivi kindergarden, Kihnu kindergar-
23.09.2024				den, Raadiku kindergarden, Seli kindergarden,
24.09.2024				Pirita kindergarden, Ülemiste kindergarden,
25.09.2024				Asunduse kindergarden, Delfiin kindergarden,
20.09.2024				Muinasjutu kindergarden, Kadaka kindergarden,
02.10.2024				Raku kindergarden, Sinilind kindergarden, Männi
03.10.2024				kindergarden, Läänemere kindergarden,
04.10.2024				Südameke kindergarden, Lepistiku kindergar-
07.10.2024				den, Kadaka kindergarden, Lehola kindergarden,
08.10.2024				Sõbrakese kindergarden, Kasekese kindergar-
09.10.2024				den, Tähekese kindergarden, Pallipõnn kinder-
10.10.2024				garden, Pirita-Kose kindergarden, Tammetõru
11.10.2024				kindergarden, Muhu kindergarden, Vesiroosi kin-
14.10.2024				dergarden, Rõõmupesa kindergarden, Päevalille
15.10.2024				kindergarden, Kiikhobu kindergarden, Mooniõied
16.10.2024				kindergarden.
17.10.2024				The 45-minute waste sorting lesson for young
18.10.2024				children was fun and interactive. Through games
21.10.2024				and hands-on activities, they learned to recog-
22.10.2024				nize different types of waste and sort them cor-
23.10.2024				rectly, making environmental awareness both
28.10.2024				engaging and age appropriate.
29.10.2024				
01.11.2024				
04.11.2024				
05.11.2024				
06.11.2024				
07.11.2024				
12.11.2024				
13.11.2024				
14.11.2024				
15.11.2024				
18.11.2024				
19.11.2024				
20.11.2024				
22.11.2024				
25.11.2024				
26.11.2024				
27.11.2024				

11.09.2024 23.09.2024 24.09.2024 01.10.2024 08.10.2024 10.10.2024 14.10.2024 15.10.2024 18.10.2024 05.11.2024 26.11.2024 27.11.2024	Waste-wolf lesson about waste sorting.	Primary school/ 1-4 th grade	7-10 years	Sakala Eragümnaasium, Nõmme primary school, Pirita Economic Gymnasium, Rahume primary school, Pääsküla primary school, Nõmme private school, Merivälja primary school, Käo Primary school, Tänismäe Gymnasium, Hiiu primary school. The 45-minute waste sorting lesson for young children was fun and interactive. Through games and hands-on activities, they learned to recognize different types of waste and sort them correctly, making environmental awareness both engaging and age appropriate.
11.11.2024	Seminar about packaging materials and waste sorting.	elementary school / 6-7 th grade	12-14 years	School visit to Tallinna Laagna Gymnasium. The seminar was engaging and inclusive, featuring a presentation that provided new insights while being closely linked to an interactive discussion. The focus was on different packaging materials, their environmental impact, and proper waste sorting practices.

ANNEX 5 – Feedback template

Feedback Survey: TREASoURcE Circular Economy Training

This survey aims to understand the impact of the TREASoURcE Circular Economy training and to gather insights for further content development.

No personal data will be collected via this form and all answers are anonymous. Responses will be treated and stored in accordance with the TREASoURcE project's Privacy Policy. For more information about the Privacy Policy: <https://treasource.eu/privacy-policy/>

1. **For which age group did you implement the circular economy training?**
2. **What aspects of the circular economy training did you find most beneficial for your students?**
3. **Can you describe any noticeable changes in your students' understanding or behavior regarding sustainability/circular economy after the training?**
4. **How do you think the training could be improved to better meet the needs of your students?**
5. **What challenges, if any, did you observe?**
6. **How would you rate the overall effectiveness of the circular economy training?**
 1. Very ineffective
 2. Ineffective
 3. Neutral
 4. Effective
 5. Very effective
7. **How likely are you to recommend this training to other teachers/educators?**
 1. Very unlikely
 2. Unlikely
 3. Neutral
 4. Likely
 5. Very likely
8. **Do you have any additional comments or suggestions for further development of the training?**